

Getting Started With Spatial omics

BioCommons Webinar

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Today's webinar

Part 1: Background

- What is spatial omics?
- Spatial technologies review
- Choosing the right spatial technology for your experiment

Part 2: Spatial omics data analysis

- Overview of spatial data and analysis ecosystems
- Spatial analysis workflow
- Key statistical concepts
- Common challenges with spatial data

Part 1

Background to spatial omics

What is spatial omics?

- Quantification of gene and/or protein expression within a tissue **while retaining spatial information**
 - *Where in a tissue is a gene or protein expressed?*

Comparing omics technologies

Bulk RNAseq

- ✓ Cost effective
- ✓ Whole transcriptome
- ✗ Averaged gene expression across whole sample → loss of single cell **and** spatial information

Comparing omics technologies

Comparing omics technologies

Chen et al. (2025); Nat Rev Clin Oncol

Choosing the right omics technology

Is spatial information needed with gene expression?

No

Yes

Is whole transcriptome analysis needed?

Are the target transcripts known?

No

Yes

No

Yes

Is the gene expression needed at single cell level resolution?

Is the region of interest known?

No

Yes

No

Yes

Microarray

Bulk RNA-seq

scRNA-seq

Seq-based spatial

Image-based spatial

ROI-based spatial

- ✓ Fast, simple
- ✓ Cost effective
- ✓ High throughput
- ✓ Targeted gene panel
- ✓ Whole transcriptome (bulk RNA-seq)
- ✗ Averaged gene expression
- ✗ No spatial information

- ✓ > 10k single-cell gene expression profiles
- ✓ Characterisation of cell types, state, lineage, cell-cell communication
- ✗ Complex, expensive
- ✗ Sample preparation can alter gene profile
- ✗ No spatial information

- ✓ Retains spatial detail
- ✓ Transcriptome profiling
- ✓ Integrate scRNA-seq
- ✓ Assess cell-cell communication
- ✗ Complex, expensive
- ✗ Time consuming

- ✓ Retains spatial detail
- ✓ Simple & cost-effective
- ✓ High throughput
- ✓ Assess cell-cell communication
- ✗ Limited number of probes - not full transcriptome

Spatial omics use case - neurobiology

STOmics Stereo-seq data. *Chen et al. (2023); Cell*

Spatial omics use case - cancer biology

Lung adenocarcinoma (Noguchi type B; Adenocarcinoma *in situ*)

10X Xenium data. Nagasawa et al. (2024); *Cancer Science*

Choosing the right omics technology

Goal	Bulk RNAseq	Single Cell RNAseq	Spotted Spatial omics	Single Cell Spatial omics
<i>Differential expression between samples</i>	✓	✓	✓	◆
<i>Characterising expression in known rare cell types</i>	✓	◆	✗	✗
<i>Expression studies with large sample sizes</i>	✓	✗	✗	✗
<i>Differential expression between cell types</i>	✗	✓	✗	◆
<i>Changes in cell type proportions</i>	✗	✓	✗	✓
<i>Characterising novel cell types</i>	✗	✓	✗	✓
<i>Examining cell type localisation</i>	✗	✗	✓	✓
<i>Examining tissue microenvironments</i>	✗	✗	✓	✓
<i>Regional expression patterns</i>	✗	✗	✓	✓

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<i>Characterising novel cell types</i>	✗	✓	✗	✓
<i>Examining cell type localisation</i>	✗	✗	✓	✓
<i>Examining tissue microenvironments</i>	✗	✗	✓	✓
<i>Regional expression patterns</i>	✗	✗	✓	✓

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<i>Regional expression patterns</i>	✗	✗	✓	✓

Sequencing-based vs. Imaging-based

Sequencing/spot-based spatial omics	Image-based spatial omics
(Visium, Stereo-seq, GeoMx)	(Xenium, CosMx, MERFISH)
Whole transcriptome	Targeted transcripts: 100 - 1000
Tissue-wide coverage, options to analyse at single-cell scale	Single-cell and subcellular resolution
“Binned”	Cells segmented
Ideal for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coarse distribution of cell/tissue types e.g. tumour microenvironment - Larger tissue samples - Unbiased, exploratory analysis, hypothesis generation 	Ideal for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Profiling cell-cell interactions - Cell type analysis - Targeted expression profiling, hypothesis testing

Spot-based spatial omics

- 'Spots' of barcoded DNA on slides
- Platforms:
 - 10X Visium
 - STOmics Stereo-seq
- PolyA capture (fresh frozen tissue) → unbiased, novel/rare transcripts
- Probe-based (fixed tissue) → human & mouse only
- Whole transcriptome coverage
- Limitation: multiple cells per spot → can confound analysis
- Example use-case: profiling full transcriptome across different brain regions in fresh frozen tissue slices

Region of interest-based spatial omics

Tissue Structures

- Bruker GeoMx
 - “Digital spatial profiler”
- Probe-based
- User-defined regions of interest (ROIs)
- Requires > dozens of cells per ROI → not single cell
 - Bulk RNA-seq + spatial information
 - Arbitrary shape & size
- Full transcriptome coverage
- Protein expression
- Example use case: examining the differential expression of genes between alpha and beta cells in pancreatic tissue

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Image-based spatial omics

- Fluorescence in-situ hybridisation (FISH)
- Sequence of probes hybridised to tissue → decode → identify 100s to 1000s of transcripts
- Protein expression via fluorescently tagged antibodies
- Platforms:
 - 10X Xenium
 - Bruker CosMx
 - Vizgen MERFISH
- Single cell/sub-cellular resolution
- No sequencing involved → images processed on-board
- No full-transcriptome coverage (yet)
- Sparse data
- Example use case: analysing immune cell activity within the tumour microenvironment, targeting genes involved in major immune cell types

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Experimental design considerations

- What's the **spatial hypothesis**? Would single cell or bulk be sufficient?
- Do I need the **panel/transcriptome**? Would targeted microscopy do?
- Are **gene(s) of interest** covered?
- Are **cell types of interest** common enough? Can they be identified?
- What **kind of tissue** do I have available? Fresh frozen vs fixed?
- What **species** am I studying? Human, mouse, other?
- **Sample size**: Balance cost vs statistical power
 - Technical variability
 - Tissue heterogeneity - consistency within tissue?
 - Biological replicates for testing - expected effect size?

Can address with a **clear biological question**,
and **ability to follow-up** results in a larger sample size

Choosing the right spatial technology

Key parameters to consider		10X Visium V.1	10X Visium V.2	GeoMx	10X Visium HD	Stereo-seq	MERFISH	10X Xenium	CosMx
Species	Human and mouse only		✓	✓	✓			✓	✓
	Any	✓				✓	✓		
Experimental aim	Hypothesis generation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
	Hypothesis testing				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Resolution	≥ 50µm	✓	✓	✓					
	Single cell scale				✓	✓			
	Single cell/subcellular						✓	✓	✓
Genes/proteins profiled	Whole transcriptome	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
	Gene panel						✓	✓	✓
	Protein panel	✓	✓	✓			✓		✓
Tissue size	≤ 6.5mm x 6.5mm	✓	✓		✓				
	> 6.5mm x 6.5mm			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
Cost relative to cells analysed	Low					✓		✓	
	Medium	✓	✓	✓					
	High				✓		✓		✓

Adapted from Lim et al. (2025); BMC Genomics

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Adapted from Lim et al. (2025); BMC Genomics

Summary

- Spatial omics technologies provide **near or true single cell** transcriptomic and/or proteomic information while **retaining spatial data**
- Valuable for studying tissue/tumour **microenvironments**, cell-cell interactions, spatial gene expression patterns
- **Spot based**: whole transcriptome coverage, greater depth, cheaper, can work with any species (fresh tissue)
- **Image-based**: sub-cellular resolution, sparse data, more expensive, no full-transcriptome coverage
- **Several platforms available**: choice depends on budget, sample size, frozen vs fixed tissue, species, and transcriptome coverage

Part 2

Spatial omics data analysis

How to prepare a spatial dataset for analysis?

Images from Seurat spatial vignette

Spatial omics analysis workflow

Spotted spatial to counts matrix

Spot based

In spot based sequencing methods, probes are counted

Simple in practice: Run tool provided

Cell segmentation

Image
based

In image-based spatial - cells are 'segmented' from the fluorescence images

- 1) Find cell
- 2) Count probes within it

Often customised for experiment

Original: Configuration A

Adjusted: Configuration D + cyto2 model

Human osteosarcoma (left) and an unspecified tissue sample with two different segmentation runs. Taken from atomx user manual.

Segmentation to counts matrix

Count transcripts

Image based

Cell #1231
3x Nrn1
2x Gad1
1x Pvalb

	gene 1	gene 2	gene 3	gene 4	gene 5	gene 6
cell 1	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange
cell 2	Light Orange					
cell 3	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange
cell 4	Light Orange					
cell 5	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange
cell 6	Light Orange					

Images from Seurat spatial vignette. Showing the process of counting genes per cell.

Cell level QC and Filtering

Are there enough transcripts in a cell to analyse? Filter out the 'bad' cells...

	Cell01	Cell02	Cell03	Cell04	Cell05	Cell06	Cell07	Cell08	Cell09	Cell10	Cell11	Cell12	Cell13	Cell14	Cell15	Cell16	Cell17	Cell18	Cell19
CXCL1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2
CXCL8	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	1
DKK2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
EGF	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
HOX11A	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	3	2
HBA1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28	0	0	0
IL5	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
IL6	4	0	2	1	9	3	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	2	0	3	0	8	0
KIT	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1
LRRTM2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NFKB1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	2
PKD2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
RPS6KA2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SIX2	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0
SNCA	0	0	1	0	0	2	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
TLR2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TLR3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
ZNF621	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	4	2

Counts matrix - table of copies of each target per cell

Distribution of transcripts per cell? A minimum of 100 transcripts indicated.

Cell level QC and filtering

Cells with few counts are difficult to analyse.

- They can cluster out, or have extreme normalised expression values
- Removing them leaves 'gaps' in the tissue.

Filter cells gently!

Probe level QC: Negative/control probes

Image based

Imaged based analyses (Xenium, cosmx, vizgen) use RNA binding probes, not sequence. Their fluorescence pattern decodes the target gene.

- Control 'negative' probes: Real probes against non-existent RNA
- 'Probes' of fluorescence codes aren't even real probes

From 10X material:

<https://www.10xgenomics.com/instruments/xenium-analyzer>

Probe QC is needed - but very dependent on technology.

Normalisation and scaling

Normalisation corrects for biases in this direction

Normalised data: compare a gene across cells or groups

Scaling corrects for biases in this direction

Scaled data: Compare cell relationships in a multi-gene way e.g. PCA, UMAP, clustering

Thanks to Laura Perlaza-Jimenez of MGBP for original slide

Dimensional reduction: UMAPs

~200 genes

~10 PCs

2 dimensions

	Cell01	Cell03	Cell05	Cell06	Cell07	Cell08	Cell09	Cell10	Cell13	Cell17	Cell18	Cell19
CXCL1	1.7	1.3	0.0	0.9	1.7	0.0	1.7	0.0	0.0	8.3	0.0	0.0
CXCL8	1.7	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	1.7	1.4	0.0	10.0	0.0	0.0
DKK2	1.7	0.0	1.0	0.9	0.0	0.0	1.7	1.4	0.0	11.7	0.0	0.0
HOX11A	1.7	2.5	2.0	0.0	1.7	4.0	0.0	1.4	0.0	15.0	0.0	0.0
IL6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	5.0	1.4	0.0	10.0	0.0	0.0
KIT	1.7	3.8	8.0	0.9	1.7	0.0	0.0	5.7	0.0	40.0	0.0	0.0
NFKB1	0.0	2.5	0.0	0.9	3.3	2.0	0.0	2.9	0.0	18.3	0.0	0.0
SIX2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
SNCA	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
ZNF621	8.3	17.5	30.0	6.4	13.3	16.0	18.3	14.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

	Cell01	Cell03	Cell05	Cell06	Cell07	Cell08	Cell09	Cell10	Cell13	Cell17	Cell18	Cell19
PC1	-1.2	6.5	2.6	0.1	0.3	1.7	4.2	-1.2	-1.2	-1.2	-1.2	-1.2
PC2	0.6	0.1	2.0	0.0	-0.3	0.1	0.4	1.2	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5
PC3	-1.1	0.4	-1.1	-1.1	0.4	1.8	1.8	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1
PC4	-0.8	-0.1	0.1	-1.7	-1.1	1.2	2.4	0.6	-2.0	-2.0	-2.0	-2.0
...												
PC50												

Find 'highly variable' genes

Principal component analysis (PCA)

Linear relationships

UMAP : Summarise the PCs into just xy coords.

Non-linear relationships

More QC: Plot everything!

Look for biases, trends that might affect analyses

- QC : Slide, total RNA, negative probes, slide, batch
- Experimental: Groups, samples, timepoint, treatment, mouse

Data from (Garrido-Trigo et al. 2023) [Macrophage and neutrophil heterogeneity at single-cell spatial resolution in human inflammatory bowel disease](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xcrp.2023.100900), reanalysed:
https://swbioinf.github.io/spatialsnippets/d_cosmxiBD.html#Basic_preprocessing

Batch correction / integration

Batch correction emphasises celltype differences

Clustering

1) PCA

	Cell01	Cell03	Cell05	Cell06	Cell07	Cell08	Cell09	Cell10	Cell13	Cell17	Cell18	Cell19
PC1	-1.2	6.5	2.6	0.1	0.3	1.7	4.2	-1.2	-1.2	-1.2	-1.2	-1.2
PC2	0.6	0.1	2.0	0.0	-0.3	0.1	0.4	1.2	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5
PC3	-1.1	0.4	-1.1	-1.1	0.4	1.8	1.8	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1
PC4	-0.8	-0.1	0.1	-1.7	-1.1	1.2	2.4	0.6	-2.0	-2.0	-2.0	-2.0
...												
PC50												

2) Cluster.

Adjust resolution as needed

Cell type annotation

Apply multiple lines of evidence;

- What **marker genes** does a cluster express?
 - Check public databases (e.g. human protein atlas)
- Use a cell typing tool (e.g. singleR) and a **known reference**
- Plot the clusters **spatially**

Broad => specific

Cell type annotation

Downstream analysis

What can you do? We have celltypes, locations of cells, locations of genes, spatial regions and niches...

Spatial sampler - a collection of howtos for various tests in spatial data

<https://swbioinf.github.io/spatialsnippets/index.html>

Downstream analysis

- **Differential expression of genes**
 - *Expression changes in T cells before and after treatment*

Downstream analysis

Identify cellular neighbourhood niches

- *Expression in T cells within tumour regions vs normal tissue*
- *Cancer cell expression in immune hot vs cold regions*

Downstream analysis

- Find genes with spatially restricted expression.
 - *Is the coexpression of Gene X and Y maintained in the knockout?*
 - *A ligand receptor pair expressed in particular celltypes?*

Spatial data analysis ecosystems

Bioconductor: R repository of many bioinformatics analysis packages. Spatial packages in Bioconductor make use of the *SpatialExperiment* or *SpatialFeatureExperiment* classes, allowing use of many existing tools.

Seurat: R package from the Satija lab that is a one-stop shop for most common spatial and single cell analysis tasks. Uses the *Seurat* class

Scanpy: Python project for spatial and single cell data analysis. There are currently two packages for spatial data analysis: *squidpy* and *spatialdata*

All are good options. Pick the one that appeals!

- Computational requirements
 - large files on disk (20-500Gb), RAM needs (16-64Gb)
 - potentially need server or HPC for certain steps.
- Proprietary toolkits for: e.g. Space Ranger from 10X

Key challenges in spatial omics analysis

Summary

- Spatial omics enables single-cell transcriptomic and/or proteomic analysis of a tissue, while retaining spatial information
 - Some common processing steps, many options for downstream analysis
- Rapidly advancing technology
- Different tools for different jobs, complementary omics
 - Choose the right technology and design for your question

Registration for hands-on workshop 28-29 Oct

(registration closes 10th October)

<https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/spatial-omics-workshop-2025>

Resources

- Seurat tutorials
 - https://satijalab.org/seurat/articles/get_started_v5_new
- Guide to (some) bioconductor spatial analysis using 'voyager' package
 - <https://pachterlab.github.io/voyager/>
- Orchestrating Single Cell analysis with bioconductor: A classic around single cell analysis in bioconductor, also applicable to spatial analyses
 - https://bioconductor.org/books/release/OSCA/?mc_cid=8aaf5a3d5a
- Human protein atlas: Useful to looking up single cell gene expression for evaluating 'marker' genes
 - <https://www.proteinatlas.org/>
- Spatial sampler - a collection of howtos for various tests in spatial data
 - <https://swbioinf.github.io/spatialsnippets/index.html>

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